

'Sort by relevance' project: Interview protocol

About this document

This is a supporting output from the project "Sort by relevance": Exploring assumptions about algorithm-mediated academic literature searches'. The project was undertaken during 2022 and funded by the Society for Research in Higher Education (SRHE).

The project was focused upon the use of ranking algorithms in academic literature searches (such as Google Scholar), and sought to explore the assumptions users hold about how the algorithms work, and the implications for practice.

This document contains the interview protocol for the semi-structured co-interpretive interviews, which were used to understand participants' perspectives on online literature searches. For further information, the project report will be available to download from the SRHE website at:

<https://srhe.ac.uk/research/completed-award-reports/> .

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Welcome and ice breaking:

Thank-you for agreeing to take part in this interview. Before we get started, I'd like to recap a little bit about the project and check that you are happy to proceed.

The interviews which we are carrying out are part of a project funded by the Society for Research in Higher Education, which is looking at how online databases like Google Scholar rank their search results according to 'relevance', what they mean by relevance, and how that is interpreted by people who use the platforms.

We carried out a survey earlier in the year, which had the objective of getting information about the range of different platforms academics use for literature searches, and some information about how and why they use those platforms. We are currently in the process of analysing the survey data. In the interviews, we want to understand your perspective of using these platforms, by carrying out some searches and talking through the results.

The interview is expected to last around 45 minutes. I will be recording the audio and video, and we will need to use screen sharing for part of the interview. I will also be using an extension which automatically generates a transcript of the audio. Can you confirm that you have received and completed the consent form, and that you are happy to proceed with the interview?

[yes]

Great, thank-you. To confirm, I will now start recording the meeting and will switch on the automatic transcription.

[check that Tactiq is running. Start recording the meeting.]

Could you confirm your current academic position and institutional affiliation please?

[participant to confirm]

For this interview, we will look at carrying out some examples of academic literature searches. We will run example searches on three platforms. Which are the three platforms you use most frequently to search for academic literature?

[participant to state their three most frequently used platforms]

Great, thanks. We'll start with [platform 1], and then look at [platform 2] and [platform 3].

Platform 1

Before we get started with the searches, could you tell me briefly why you choose to use this platform?

What are the benefits and limitations of using this platform? What do you do to make up for any limitations?

Thank-you. I'd now like you to carry out some searches for me. I'll give you some guidance, but first, could you open a new tab and navigate to [platform 1] please.

[Wait until completed] Now, could you start screen sharing please.

Great. Now, I would like you to run a search query on [platform 1]. Choose a search term that is familiar to you and highly relevant to your research area, - exactly which term to use is your choice. Please enter your chosen term, and run the search.

[Wait until completed]. Great. Could you confirm what the search results are ranked by, by default?

[If it is not ranked by 'relevance' by default, then ask the participant to see if there is the option to rank by relevance, and to change to this.]

I'd like you to take a moment to look at the first page of search results. Could you talk me through the first page of results please?

Are the papers listed here the ones you would expect to be 'most relevant' or not?

How do you think 'relevance' is defined here? Why do you think some are ranked more highly than others?

In your opinion, is this a good reflection of the field or are there limitations?

What are the pros and cons of this ranking?

Now, I would like you to run a search on a specific term. We will ask all the participants to search for the same term, to see if there is any evidence that different people receive different results.

Please enter "climate change" (with quotation marks) and run the search. Now, could you select and copy the list of search results from the first page, and paste it into a Word document. [We will do this for the other platforms too; could you send me the document at the end of the interview].

Repeat for the second and third platforms.